

COMPARATIVE EVALUATION OF DIAGNOSTIC METHODS FOR BRUCellosIS IN LIVESTOCK: A COMPREHENSIVE ANALYSIS

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Abstract

Brucellosis, a zoonotic disease caused by the Brucella species, presents a considerable threat to livestock health and public safety worldwide. Brucellosis is a major health concern in developing countries, including India, where it poses serious challenges to both livestock and human populations. This article aims to provide a comprehensive analysis of various diagnostic methods employed for brucellosis in livestock. The sensitivity, specificity, and practicality of these diagnostic approaches are compared to identify optimal strategies for early detection and management in livestock populations, ultimately contributing to improved animal health and food safety. The Rose Bengal Plate Test (RBPT) and the Milk Ring Test (MRT) are the most commonly used serological tests for the diagnosis of the disease, whereas i-ELISA is the most widely used molecular diagnostic method. Molecular diagnostics, such as PCR, RT-PCR, and PCR-MS, generate rapid results with similar sensitivity but with low sensitivity at times. In conclusion, the RBPT stands out as the most appropriate diagnostic method for the detection and management of brucellosis in animals, primarily due to its well-established high sensitivity and specificity.

Keywords - zoonotic disease, Molecular diagnostics, PCR, RT-PCR, and PCR-MS.

Introduction

Brucellosis, a zoonotic disease caused by the *Brucella* species, presents a considerable threat to livestock health and public safety worldwide. It was first identified by David Bruce in 1887 (1). Due to its varied clinical presentations, it can become a serious source of economic loss for the agricultural sector by lowering productivity and raising veterinary costs. However, correct diagnosis is important because brucellosis has many symptoms that overlap with other diseases, making clinical assessments troublesome (2).

In livestock, brucellosis primarily affects reproductive systems, leading to abortion, infertility, and reduced milk (3). The disease's transmission occurs mainly through consumption of unpasteurized dairy products or direct contact with infected animals, making it a persistent threat in regions where livestock farming is prevalent (4). Given the public health implications and the potential for zoonotic transmission to humans, effective diagnostic methods are essential for controlling and managing brucellosis outbreaks.

This article aims to provide a comprehensive analysis of various diagnostic methods employed for brucellosis in livestock. It will evaluate traditional serological tests such as the Rose Bengal test and serum agglutination test alongside modern molecular techniques like polymerase chain reaction (PCR). By comparing the sensitivity, specificity, and practicality of these diagnostic approaches, this study seeks to identify optimal strategies for early detection and management of brucellosis in livestock populations, ultimately contributing to improved animal health and food safety.

2. Brucellosis in Livestock: Overview

Brucellosis is a major concern in developing countries, including India, where it poses serious challenges to both livestock and human populations. Brucellosis does not leave a single country in the world and affects various species of animals. However, domestic livestock species like cattle, buffalo, yak, sheep, and goats are the main sources of zoonotic transmission to humans via direct or indirect contact (5).

In livestock, brucellosis causes premature abortion and retained placenta in the infected animals, resulting in low productivity (3). Economic loss associated with the disease depends on the prevalence, control strategies, and animal productivity. Brucellosis not only affects the welfare of the

animals but also impacts the country's animal agriculture economic output.

2.1. Etiology

Brucellosis is primarily caused by various species of the *Brucella* genus, which are gram-negative, non-motile bacteria. The most common species affecting livestock include *Brucella abortus*, *Brucella melitensis*, and *Brucella suis*. Among these, *B. abortus* is typically linked to cattle, *B. melitensis* is recognized as the most virulent and widespread species worldwide, while *B. suis* is predominantly associated with pigs. These pathogens are capable of surviving within host cells, particularly in macrophages, allowing them to evade the host's immune response and establish chronic infections. (2, 6, 7)

2.2. Transmission

Brucellosis spreads mainly through direct contact with infected animals or contaminated materials (2). The infection can be acquired in livestock by ingesting contaminated feeds or water, by aerosol inhalation, or by skin abrasions (8). Infected animals secrete the bacteria in several body fluids, including milk, urine, and tissue and mucus of reproductive organs. This secures the bacteria with enhanced transmission in herds. Reproductive tissues from aborted fetuses are especially very virulent, posing a great danger at any time during pregnancy, lambing, or calving (9).

2.3. Pathogenesis

Brucella gains access to the host through various pathways, including contaminated food or water, inhalation, and direct interaction with infected tissues. It predominantly targets professional phagocytes like macrophages and dendritic cells, evading initial immune defenses. The bacteria reside in specialized vacuoles called *Brucella*-containing vacuoles (BCVs), where they multiply and modify the host's immune responses. *Brucella* suppresses lysosomal fusion with BCVs, allowing survival and multiplication within macrophages. It then spreads through the lymphatic and circulatory systems, infecting organs and causing reproductive complications in livestock. *Brucella* employs mechanisms to avoid the immune response, interfering with dendritic cell maturation and antigen presentation. This manipulation hinders the host's adaptive immune response. The chronic infection leads to severe health problems and economic loss in livestock. Understanding the pathogenesis is crucial

for developing diagnostic tools and control strategies to manage brucellosis in livestock (8, 10).

2.4. Epidemiology and Impact in Livestock Health

Brucellosis is a major health concern worldwide, especially in developing countries with a strong livestock culture. Infection rates vary across different species of livestock. Seroprevalence is around 7.55% in cattle and lower in sheep and goats. A survey in Rajasthan, India showed a prevalence of 7.00% in cattle, 2.43% in sheep, and 0.58% in goats (11). Transmission dynamics of brucellosis are influenced by factors such as herd management, vaccination levels, and animal density. In areas with high livestock density, the risk of infection increases due to close contact among animals. Juvenile animals are more affected than adults, and female animals suffer from reproductive issues related to the disease (5, 12).

The impacts of brucellosis on livestock include reproductive failures, decreased milk production, and financial losses for agricultural producers. It is a contagious disease that can spread quickly within a herd, resulting in severe consequences.

3. Diagnostic Methods for Brucellosis

Brucellosis is one of the principal bacterial infections in the livestock management sector, with possible economic impacts caused by the *Brucella* species. Accurate diagnosis is important to efficient control and eradication. The methodology used in diagnosing brucellosis broadly can be categorized into serological tests, molecular techniques and bacteriological culture.

3.1. Serological Tests

Serological assays are highly used for screening and diagnosis of brucellosis. These assays detect antibodies that are produced in response to the infection. Diagnosing individual animals requires these assays, as well as in conducting herd assessments. In India, serological examinations such as RBPT, i-ELISA, CFT, BPAT, and MRT are essential in the diagnosis of brucellosis in livestock. Although RBPT yields prompt outcomes, i-ELISA presents improved specificity and sensitivity, rendering it progressively preferred within diagnostic methodologies. The incorporation of these tests into thorough surveillance initiatives is crucial for the efficient management and prevention of brucellosis throughout the nation. (2, 13, 14)

3.1.1. Rose Bengal Plate Test (RBPT)

The Rose Bengal Plate Test, RBPT, is an agglutination test that is quick and simple and is commonly used as an initial screening test for brucellosis (5). It is performed by adding serum samples to a standardized *Brucella abortus* antigen stained with Rose Bengal dye.

Method: Equal volumes of the serum and antigen are mixed on a glass surface. Subsequently, some gentle agitation is done, and one observes the mixture for agglutination. Any amount of agglutination presence signifies a positive result.

Performance: In the test done in Rajasthan, RBPT reported a seroprevalence in about 5.06% of livestock (15). Although useful for preliminary screening, RBPT has the disadvantage of sometimes producing false positives because of cross-reactivity with other bacteria (11).

3.1.2. Indirect Enzyme-Linked Immunosorbent Assay (i-ELISA)

One of the important serological tests conducted in India, that is, i-ELISA—a significant indirect enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay. It has better specificity and sensitivity than traditional methods (16).

Procedure: This is the test for detecting IgG antibodies against *Brucella* spp. through specific antigens, coated on microplates, and measuring the OD to provide evidence for the presence of antibodies.

Performance: Another study from Rajasthan also obtained a seroprevalence of 6.88% by i-ELISA, thus suggesting that it is sensitive in differentiating *Brucella* antibodies from those elicited against cross-reacting pathogens like *Yersinia enterocolitica* (15, 11). This is very

important to eliminate the false positivity which may be obtained when using RBPT.

3.1.3. Complement Fixation Test (CFT)

Although rarely employed nowadays, the Complement Fixation Test may be useful to confirm brucellosis diagnosis.

Procedure: CFT measures the ability of antibodies in serum to fix complement when mixed with specific antigens. A lack of hemolysis indicates a positive result.

Limitations: The complexity and time requirements of CFT exceed those of RBPT or i-ELISA, consequently restricting its implementation in routine field applications.

3.1.4. Milk Ring Test (MRT)

The Milk Ring Test (MRT) is purposefully developed for the identification of brucellosis within dairy populations.

Procedure: The *Brucella* antigen is added to bulk tank milk samples. The samples are subjected to centrifugation, and agglutination at the milk-water interface is checked.

Importance: MRT acts as a good detector of infected herds, thus controlling the disease in the affected animals.

3.2. Molecular Techniques

Molecular diagnostics have surfaced as important probes to identify *Brucella* species, thus speeding the detection of pathogens and raising success in rapid diagnosis. In India, in that regard, various molecular methods are used for diagnosing brucellosis in livestock, providing further effectiveness to conventional serological assays.

Molecular diagnostics, primarily in the form of different types of PCR, is becoming increasingly important for the diagnosis of brucellosis in livestock in India. As they are sensitive and specific tests compared to conventional serological techniques, they facilitate earlier and more accurate detection of the infections (11). Therefore, incorporation of these molecular methods into routine diagnostic algorithms plays a key role in the effective management and control strategies against brucellosis in livestock populations.

3.2.1. Polymerase Chain Reaction (PCR)

The PCR technique is the most versatile method in the molecular diagnosis of brucellosis. Since PCR allows for the amplification of specific DNA sequences, it makes possible *Brucella* DNA detection in blood, tissues, and milk samples.

Types of PCR

Conventional PCR: The focus of conventional PCR lies upon specific genes such as *bcbp31*, *omp2*, and the 16S rRNA. Studies show that conventional PCR has a higher sensitivity and specificity, which makes it useful for the detection of acute and chronic infections (11, 15).

Real-Time PCR: This technologically advanced type of PCR yields quantitative results and prevents contamination since it uses closed systems. It is targeted toward conserved regions such as the insertion sequence IS711, which was reported to be faster and far more sensitive than classical methods (17, 18).

Performance: A PCR study conducted in Rajasthan found a seroprevalence of 1.27% among samples of the animals that were under investigation; hence, it was found helpful to validate brucellosis cases ascertained through serological tests (15). The sensitivity of PCR is reportedly high: 5 to 50 *Brucella* colony-forming units (CFU) per milliliter of sample may be detected (19).

3.3. Bacteriological Culture

Bacteriological culture is still the backbone in the diagnosis of brucellosis in livestock since it can directly isolate and identify *Brucella* species. In confirmation of infection, it thus always finds use together with serological tests in full diagnosis.

Bacteriological culture remains the cornerstone of the diagnosis of brucellosis in animal species. It is sensitive, but it requires proper handling and very specific conditions to provide positive results. However, its ability to identify *Brucella* species at a species level makes

it particularly important for clinical and epidemiological work. The adoption of advanced techniques like lysis-centrifugation and clot culture enhances its sensitivity, especially in poorly resourced settings where automated systems may be lacking.

Culture typically begins with the correct sample collection. Samples may come from several sources such as blood, tissue, and milk. The samples should be handled aseptically and cooled or frozen immediately if cultured within 12 hours to prevent degradation of the organisms.

The choice of the culture media is important in the successful isolation of *Brucella*. Some of the commonly recommended media are Trypticase Soy Agar (TSA), Blood Agar Base (BAB), and Columbia Agar. These can then be enriched with 2-5% equine or bovine serum to encourage the growth of specific *Brucella* strains. The alternative is using selective media that discourage contaminants from growing by using antibiotics or antifungals.

Cultural Methodologies

Direct Isolation: Samples can be inoculated into the agar/semisolid media, and the opportunity for colonies to grow will facilitate their successful isolation and identification. Colonies are normally smooth, translucent, and pale honey-colored and have a convex morphology after incubation at 37°C in an atmosphere enriched with 5-10% CO₂.

Biphasic Culture Method (Castañeda Method): This method involves inoculating blood samples into a biphasic culture of liquid broth and solid agar. Incubation is done in controlled conditions with daily checks for growth. With this strategy, recovery rates can be enhanced since it also provides both aerobic and anaerobic conditions.

Lysis-Centrifugation Method: This technique involves lysis of leukocytes in blood specimens with the aim of releasing phagocytosed *Brucella* bacteria before cultivation on appropriate media. Studies show that this method significantly improves the rate of isolation and shortens the time required for detection compared to conventional techniques.

Clot culture method: Blood clots are disturbed and put into culture media. This method is particularly useful when it is challenging to obtain extra blood samples. In some cases, it is documented to produce positive results much faster than traditional methods.

Identification of Isolates

Once colonies are acquired, identification requires several steps.

Morphological examination: Gram staining or Stain's modification of the Ziehl-Neelsen method aid in visualizing the characteristic shape of coccobacilli *Brucella* forms.

Biochemical tests used are the urease and oxidase tests to differentiate *Brucella* from other contaminants.

Serological assays, specifically slide agglutination tests employing polyclonal anti-*Brucella* serum, can verify the identity of isolated colonies.

4. Criteria for Evaluation

Main criteria for the evaluation of an ideal diagnostic method include sensitivity and specificity because they are most vital for evaluating a test. A good diagnostic method correctly identifies the true positive sample (sensitivity); a good diagnostic method correctly identifies the true negative sample (specificity). The costs of a test are also very important, especially in a veterinary setting where money is sometimes scarce. Thus, tests that are relatively expensive may, in practice, be underutilized. In addition, the results from a test are only useful if they are available in a reasonable amount of time – say one to three days depending on the disease. If it takes longer, the usefulness of the result is marginal. In addition, field-use tests are preferred because of the potential for large numbers of analyses.

These tests should not require specialist facilities, may often be able to do accurate and sensitive tests at a competitive price, but because they are not widely recognized and specific tests, the test will be evaluated. It should be pointed out again that a good or a bad overall rating is difficult, as this depends largely on the conditions of the investigation. The tests

must compete depending on the needs of the people who use tests for investigations. In livestock diagnostics, for example, the test does not require extensive testing and that specific test can deliver results for a few animals in hours. We need to investigate the test in terms of livestock, and we must carefully evaluate not only whether the test differentiates between reality and health, but whether or not it is practical to implement it in larger investigations. There should be a diagnostic practice. In order to evaluate the test, we must first create an effective framework in terms of the diagnostic evaluation.

4.1. Sensitivity and Specificity

Two well-established major properties of diagnostic tests are sensitivity and specificity. Sensitivity quantifies the capacity of a particular test to identify infected animals correctly. Likewise, specificity, a measure of the capacity of a diagnostic test to accurately identify non-disease individuals, is defined as the proportion of true negative individuals identified by the test, with the false positive rate as its complement.

Sensitivity and specificity indicate the technical characteristics of diagnostic tests thought to be applicable in defining the ability of a diagnostic method. The use of diagnostics with lower specificity will result in the culling of animals that are incorrectly interpreted as infected, and positive economic benefit may also be derived from such policy, particularly in the presence of high-value animals and/or expensive drug administration. Additionally, false positive tests may lead to the remainder of the herd needing to be slaughtered. Consequently, the need for high sensitivity or specificity varies according to the diagnostic requirements and clinical settings. Regardless, false negative diagnoses can have serious consequences, particularly if they lead to the consumption of high-risk animal products from infectious animals, while false positive results generate rather movement controls than clinical disease consequences for the individual animal.

For these reasons, it is important that the diagnostic methods have been validated against established gold standards with well-recognized performance. If a method is not sensitive, and a false negative animal is left in the herd from which the pathogen is withdrawn and transmitted to humans, then this may undermine public health. Furthermore, 'false negative' tests have animal welfare implications as they may result in infected animals not being given treatment and, in addition, potential spread of the pathogen to other animals, to wildlife, and through trade.

Serological Tests

Rose Bengal Plate Test RBPT

Sensitivity: RBPT shows high sensitivity rates and is often reported to be 96% or more in different studies, and it is an effective tool for screening brucellosis in livestock (20, 21).

Specificity: It shows a specificity of 100% especially for the process of differentiating between individuals infected and non-infected (20, 21).

Indirect enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (i-ELISA)

Sensitivity: The sensitivity of the i-ELISA assay ranges from 60% to 98% because it depends on the stage of infection and the population being examined (20).

Specificity: Specificity is generally around 80%, which is lower than that of RBPT but still acceptable in many contexts (20).

Complement Fixation Test (CFT)

However, CFT is used conventionally and is less favored as it involves complexity and longer turnaround times. It has very variable sensitivity and specificity values; however, it is considered less sensitive compared to RBPT.

Milk Ring Test

It is mainly used for dairy cattle, showing quite good sensitivity around 80% but less specificity because of cross-reactivity with other pathogens.

Molecular Techniques

Polymerase Chain Reaction (PCR)

Sensitivity : PCR methods have variable sensitivity ranging from 64% to 96% depending on the specific assay and sample used (22, 23). The

sensitivity of real-time PCR assays, particularly when targeting specific genes (such as BCSP31), may be improved.

Specificity: PCR specificity can vary, but in some studies, it has been reported to reach 100% with the application of validated protocols (19, 22). However, this may lead to contamination risks affecting the outcome.

Bacteriological Cultivation

Bacteriological culture is still the gold standard for diagnosing brucellosis.

Sensitivity: Culture methods typically have a sensitivity of around 77%, which can be influenced by the stage of infection and sample handling (22).

Specificity: Culture techniques are 100% specific since the techniques only confirm the presence of the live bacteria.

Table-1: Table showing the estimated cost of diagnostic tests (24, 25)_

Diagnostic Test	Cost (In Rs. per sample) by ICAR-IVRI (June 2024)	Cost (In Rs. per sample) by ICAR-NIVEDI with effect from 01.09.2023
RBPT	200 Rs	150
ELISA	400 Rs	250
CFT	-	-
MRT	200	150
PCR	700	500
Bacteriological Culture	300	-

In conclusion, serological tests like the Rose Bengal Plate Test (RBPT) and the Milk Ring Test (MRT) have a crucial role in the diagnosis of brucellosis in animals mainly due to their economic effectiveness. In contrast, bacteriological culture is used less frequently since it has higher costs, and molecular techniques, such as PCR, are the costliest diagnostic methods available.

4.3. Field Applicability

Field applicability is important in the comparison of veterinary diagnostic tests because it facilitates rapid disease detection, allowing for quick diagnosis and intervention to curb disease spread and reduce economic losses. Tests should be accessible and easy to use, enabling operation by non-experts in remote locations with limited laboratory access. Cost-effectiveness is another critical factor, as field tests typically cost less, promoting wider use among farmers and veterinarians in resource-limited areas. Additionally, field applicability allows for real-time monitoring, which is essential for prompt responses to health threats and effective outbreak management. Ensuring reliable test performance and accuracy across various environments is vital for maintaining validation and quality control. Finally, integrating these tests with surveillance systems empowers ongoing monitoring of animal health, facilitating early detection and data collection during outbreaks.

Serological Tests

Rose Bengal Plate Test RBPT

Field Applicability: RBPT is a rapid and cost-effective test which can be conducted in the field with minimal equipment. The simplicity of test

Table No. 2 Summary Table Based on Criteria Used for Evaluation

Summary Table Based on Criteria Used for Evaluation				
Diagnostic Method	Sensitivity	Specificity	Cost (In Rs. per sample) by ICAR-IVRI (June 2024)	Field Applicability
RBPT	96%	100%	200 Rs	High
ELISA	60-98%	80%	400 Rs	Moderate
CFT	Variable	Variable	-	Low
MRT	~80%	Variable	200	High
PCR	Up to 96%	High Up to 100%	700	Low
Bacteriological Culture	Low (~77%)	100%	300	Not Applicable

In summary, serological diagnostics, such as RBPT, are quite sensitive and specific for preliminary assessments, whereas molecular diagnostics, such as PCR, generate quick results with similar sensitivity but with low sensitivity at times. Bacterial culture is the standard method of diagnosis, but it shows poor sensitivity in many cases. If all these diagnostic tools are combined, it may give the most inclusive approach to solving brucellosis in livestock flocks.

4.2. Cost-effectiveness

The cost-effective use of diagnostic methods for brucellosis is a major concern for veterinarians and livestock producers. The reasons for choosing a particular diagnostic method are multifaceted and depend on numerous issues, including farmers' financial status, the prevalence of brucellosis, and veterinarians' concerns regarding sensitivity and specificity.

allows rapid screening of large populations, making it particularly suitable for rural veterinary practices.

Indirect enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (i-ELISA)

Field Applicability: The use of i-ELISA requires specialized equipment and trained personnel, which might limit its availability for use in remote areas. However, it can be applied to identify specific antibodies, making it useful for the confirmation of brucellosis in suspected cases.

Complement Fixation Test (CFT)

Field Applicability: CFT is complex and requires a lot of time, making it less practical to employ in the field. The variable sensitivity and specificity also limit its use as a standalone diagnostic tool.

Milk Ring Test

Field Applicability: MRT can be particularly useful in the dairy cattle population and can be done rapidly in the field.

Molecular Techniques

Polymerase Chain Reaction (PCR)

Field Applicability: Requires specific equipment and trained operators, which limits its use in rural areas. The sensitivity of the tests and the requirement for strict laboratory conditions make it less suitable for field use.

Bacteriological Cultivation

Field Applicability: Bacteriological culture remains the gold standard in the diagnosis of brucellosis, but this is not practical to apply in field conditions due to time required to achieve its isolation and identification.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the RBPT stands out as the most appropriate diagnostic method for brucellosis in animals, primarily due to its well-established high sensitivity, specificity, cost effectiveness, and suitability for field application. Although i-ELISA provides superior confirmatory abilities, it is restricted in rural areas because it requires highly specialized and specific equipment. PCR and bacteriological cultures are useful tools for making confirmatory diagnoses, but they are not feasible for routine field application because of their high costs and technical requirements. Therefore, there is a need to focus on a combination of serological tests, viz., RBPT and MRT, for efficient management of brucellosis in the country's livestock across India.

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